

PNS Optimized Pulses for EPI (POPE): Simple adjustment to gradient pulse shape for practical high-resolution fMRI

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Short Synopsis 40 (words)

While gradients are getting more powerful, PNS becomes increasingly relevant for high-resolution EPI. Here, we propose a simple modification of EPI pulse shapes that reduce slew rates exclusively at peak times. This allows us to achieve robust 0.3mm fMRI.

Synopsis (100 words, without titles)

Motivation: With improvements in gradient amplifiers, clinical 7T MRI scanners (Terra.X) can now achieve slew rates up to 250T/m/s. However, full gradient performance cannot be exploited in high-resolution EPI due peripheral nerve stimulation (PNS) limits.

Goal: We characterize and mitigate these PNS constraints using a simple sequence modification: PNS-optimized EPI gradient pulse shapes.

Approach: *PNS-Optimized Pulses for EPI (POPE)*: we selectively reduce the slew rate gradient pulses at periods of high predicted PNS spikes, while leaving the rest of the waveform unchanged.

Results: While being simple, POPE yields substantial performance improvements. It provides robust fMRI protocols with 0.3mm isotropic voxels without increase in artifacts.

Impact: POPE facilitates increases in spatial resolution that were previously unattainable on clinical 7T MRI systems due to PNS limitations.

Purpose (750 words)

Mesoscale fMRI at sub-millimeter resolutions has the potential to address questions on intracortical vascular physiology and directional neural information flow across laminar microcircuits. Most human mesoscale fMRI imaging is being performed at ‘clinical’ 7T scanners with body gradients with increasingly stronger gradient amplifiers (such as the Terra.X with 135 mT/m gradient strength and 250 T/m/s slew rate). However, with increasing gradient performance, high resolution protocols are becoming increasingly limited by peripheral nerve stimulation (PNS). In EPI fMRI protocols, PNS thresholds are usually exceeded at the end of the ramp periods and need to be mitigated by costly reductions of the sequence performance such as the protocols’ overall slew rates (gradient mode) or gradient magnitude (bandwidth) Fig. 1.

Here, we seek to evaluate and optimize EPI pulse shapes for their PNS, following (Zhang 2002, Tan 2019, Middione 2020, Loecher 2020, Schulte 2014).

Upon successful conceptualization, implementation, and validation of PNS optimized gradient wave forms, we seek to use it to overcome previous spatial resolution limits of clinical 7Ts (Huber 2024).

Methods

We simulated and tested identical gradient pulses at two common 7T scanner models (Siemens Healthineers, Forchheim, Germany):

- Terra.X-VA60A gradient W60 (250T/m/s), MGH MGB.
- Terra.X-VA60A gradient XR (200T/m/s), BWH MGB.

For PNS simulations, we used the SAFE model (Stimulation Approximation by Filtering and Evaluation, (Hebrank & Gephardt, 2000)), from GitHub (Szczepankiewicz 2018).

We investigated conventional EPI pulse shapes of symmetric trapezoidal pulses and asymmetric pulses (Fig. 2A). Slew rates remained constant during sampling for “Cartesian” regridding.

The key insight to POPE is that each ramp in an EPI-readout causes a short spike of the PNS level. For trapezoidal gradient trains, these spikes limit the slew rate of the whole readout, although the threshold is reached only for a short fraction of time. The idea of POPE is to use the maximal slew rate till 98% of the threshold is reached and then reduce to a “steady-state” slew rate that keeps a constant PNS level. This results in plateaus of the PNS estimates near-threshold and lets one realize a higher average slew rate and larger gradient moments (spatial resolution) than would be allowed for a linear ramp.

N=6 participants were scanned with a custom 64ch 7T coil (Mareyam 2020):

Testing artifact level of POPE:

The effect of asymmetric artifacts were empirically investigated with resting-state EPI at 0.8mm and identical echo spacing (1.26ms) that can be executed with and without POPE (Fig. 2B).

Applying POPE to push spatial resolution to 0.3mm human fMRI:

- 0.3mm iso, matrix 420×420×18.
- TR 6.2s
- FOV 130mm, gradient 41.9mT/m matched for minimal $2\mu\text{s}$ dwell time.
- $1 \times 3_{z1}$ CAIPI undersampling, segmentation 18 (Stirnberg 2021) = shot-selective CAIPI (Hendriks 2020) 6 shots per k_z -plane
- Partial Fourier 77% (EPI factor 18)
- Prescription was auto-aligned run-to-run (Wighton 2024).
- 4-5 runs of 12min with flickering checkerboards (30s).
- Parameter list:
https://github.com/layerfMRI/Sequence_Github/blob/master/POPE/FRISGO_20251008_AZM_AA.pdf
- Open data: <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/0A2ZOK>
- Regridding for ramp-up and ramp-down in vendor reconstruction.
- GRAPPA kernel fitting in IcePat using dual-polarity averaged ACS data.

Results

Simulation results revealed the maximal ramp times at 250T/m/s before PNS thresholds are reached and subsequent steady-state values (Tab. 1). For subsequent optimization, we used:

- W60: ramp time 0.24ms with 250T/m/s and 135T/m/s steady state slew rate
- XR: ramp time 0.35ms with 200T/m/s and 135T/m/s steady state slew rate

We find that POPE can reduce the PNS estimates by 22% for the same resolution and echo spacing, without artifact level increase (Fig. 2B).

We find that POPE allows 0.30mm iso with good EPI quality (Fig. 4). Thus, robust activation could be detected across participants (Fig. 5).

We found that the gradient temperature could not be maintained at a sustainable level below 60°C, if 250T/m/s maximal slewing was used for POPE. 6-minutes cool-down periods were needed between runs

No participant reported the sensation of PNS at any experiments.

Discussion and summary

High-resolution fMRI with the latest generation of clinical 7T scanners is significantly limited by induced and estimated PNS, prohibiting the field to embrace modern hardware capabilities. We developed a simple modification in the EPI gradient pulse shape to mitigate PNS solely at the time points of PNS peaks. This allows 0.3mm fMRI precision mapping in 3D. While a conventional 3mm voxel contains $\approx 700,000$ neurons (Logothetis 2008), POPE's 0.3mm voxels are specific to ≈ 700 neurons per voxel.

Acknowledgements (no work count limit)

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Conflict of interest statement

The work presented here may be specific to the PNS safety models used in SIEMENS Healthineers' UHF scanners. This vendor is used in 83% of all human layer-fMRI papers (source: www.layerfmri.com/papers).

Dominik Rattenbacher is an employee of SIEMENS Healthineers.

References (no work count limit)

- **Hebrank**, F.X., Gebhardt, M., 2000. SAFE-Model - A New Method for Predicting Peripheral Nerve Stimulations in MRI. ISMRM Denver, 2007. <https://cds.ismrm.org/ismrm-2000/PDF7/2007.PDF>
- **Hendriks**, A. D., D'Agata, F., Raimondo, L., Schakel, T., Geerts, L., Luijten, P. R., Klomp, D. W. J., & Petridou, N. (2020). Pushing functional MRI spatial and temporal resolution further: High-density receive arrays combined with shot-selective 2D CAIPIRINHA for 3D echo-planar imaging at 7 T. *NMR in Biomedicine*, 33(5), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nbm.4281>
- **Huber**, R., Koehler, M., Stirnberg, R., Evans, J., Knudsen, L., Tyler, A., Feinberg, D., Handwerker, D., Rubin, M., Akin, B., Swegle, S., Bandettini, P., 2025. Advanced Echo-planar Parallel Imaging with Gradient-harmonization (FRISGO): an optimization strategy for fast high-resolution fMRI, in: ISMRM. p. 1262. <https://layerfmri.page.link/AEPIG>
- **Koiso**, K., Müller, A.K., Akamatsu, K., Dresbach, S., Gulban, O.F., Goebel, R., Miyawaki, Y., Poser, B.A., Huber, L., 2023. Acquisition and processing methods of whole-brain layer-fMRI

VASO and BOLD: The Kenshu dataset. *Aperture Neuro* 34.

<https://doi.org/10.52294/001c.87961>

- **Loecher** M, Middione MJ, Ennis DB. A gradient optimization toolbox for general purpose time-optimal MRI gradient waveform design. *Magn Reson Med*. 2020; 84: 3234–3245. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.28384>
- **Logothetis**, N.K., 2008. What we can do and what we cannot do with fMRI. *Nature* 453, 869–878. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature06976>
- **Mareyam**, A., Kirsch, Chang, Madan, Wald, 2020. A 64-Channel 7T array coil for accelerated brain MRI, in: ISMRM. p. 0764. <https://cds.ismrm.org/protected/20MProceedings/PDFfiles/0764.html>
- **Middione** MJ, Loecher M, Moulin K, Ennis DB. Optimization methods for magnetic resonance imaging gradient waveform design. *NMR in Biomedicine*. 2020; 33:e4308. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nbm.4308>
- **Schulte**, R.F., Noeske, R., 2014. PNS-Optimal Gradient Waveform Design. ISMRM 4252. <https://cds.ismrm.org/protected/14MProceedings/PDFfiles/4252.pdf?hl=en-US>
- **Szczepankiewicz**, F., 2018. Prediction of PNS in Siemens MRI systems (SAFE model). Github. https://github.com/filip-szczepankiewicz/safe_pns_prediction
- **Szczepankiewicz**, F., 2021. Gradient waveform design for tensor-valued encoding in diffusion MRI. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jneumeth.2020.109007>
- **Stirnberg**, R., Stöcker, T., 2021. Segmented K-Space Blipped-Controlled Aliasing in Parallel Imaging (Skipped-CAIPI) for High Spatiotemporal Resolution Echo Planar Imaging. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine* 85, 1540–1551. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.06.08.140699>
- **Tan**, E.T., Hua, Y., Fiveland, E.W., Vermilyea, M.E., Piel, J.E., Park, K.J., Ho, V.B., Foo, T.K.F., 2019. Peripheral nerve stimulation limits of a high amplitude and slew rate magnetic field gradient coil for neuroimaging. *Magn Reson Med*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mrm.27909>
- **Tekin**, Ugurdag, Guérin. Optimization of Asymmetric EPI Waveforms with Reduced Peripheral Nerve Stimulation, 2026 ISMRM submitted.
- **Wightton**, P., Hinds O., Frost R, Hoffmann M, Gagoski B, Varadarajan D, Proulx S, Reuter M, Polimeni JP, Fischl B, Ghosh S, van der Kouwe A., MR software tools for real-time decision making and FOV prescription, ISMRM, 2024 #4676. https://cds.ismrm.org/protected/24MProceedings/PDFfiles/4676_EYHb4cRdW.html
- **Zhang**, B., McKinnon, G., Rutt, B.K., 2002. Peripheral-Nerve-Stimulation-Optimized Gradient Waveform Design. ISMRM. <https://cds.ismrm.org/ismrm-2002/PDF3/0706.PDF>

5 Figures

Fig. 1: Background on PNS limits of trapezoidal EPI.

PNS estimates of high-resolution EPI can exceed the thresholds at the end of each ramp period. While PNS thresholds are only exceeded for very short periods of the readout train, to make such protocols runnable, the entire readout needs to be decelerated. E.g. reducing gradient amplitude (bandwidth) or reducing the sequence’s max slew rate (gradient mode). Both of these strategies pay a price in efficiency and achievable resolution.

Fig. 2A : Proposed EPI gradient pulse modifications in POPE.

The POPE method proposes to exclusively decelerate those parts of the EPI pulses that are affected by PNS thresholds. Resulting in asymmetric trapezoidal gradient pulse shapes.

Fig. 2B. EPI artifact level with and without POPE.

The ghost level of the asymmetric regridding was compared to the conventional approach in two participants. While small off-resonance artifacts are visible, no additional artifacts from POPE are apparent.

	XA60A	XA60A-SP04
Time of 250 T/m/s slew until PNS threshold is reached	0.245 ms	0.3 ms
Maximal slew rate that can be maintained at 99% PNS	135 T/m/s	145 T/m/s

Tab. 1 (as Fig. 3): This table shows simulation results of largest PNS-sustainable ramp times and slew rates for two current 7T systems. The ramp time refers to the period in which the gradients can be slewing at maximal rates (250T/m/s) before 98% of the PNS threshold is reached. The shown slew rates can be sustained at this 98% PNS level without further increase. These values are used to tune the EPI pulse shapes. The two SAFE model versions refer to the current Terra.X scanners from SIEMENS.

The performance of the asymmetric regridding (within the vendor's IcePat reconstruction) was compared to the conventional approach of conventional symmetric ramp sampling EPI with identical echo spacing. Data from two participants are shown for each case. The ghost magnitude refers to the magnitude difference of EPI with inverted read polarities. While small off-resonance artifacts are visible, no additional artifacts from POPE are apparent.

POPE allows fMRI at 0.3mm iso voxels: QA of protocol

A) Prescription with participant-specific auto-align

B) Motion GIF across runs. Note the different motion within the brain and skull

C) Fuzzy Ripples were reduced with LN2_FRISGO

D) High tSNR was achieved with 64ch "Azma Coil"

E) Single TR

F) run average

G) tSNR

H) functional activation

zoomed section

I) Variability GIF in averaged run.

J) POPE allows to push the gradients outside the regime of sustainable temperatures

Cooling cannot keep up with POPE's duty cycle. For safe operation, 6 min inter-run cool-down periods are needed. Also, ADC cannot keep up with POPE; current limits are min dwell time of 2 μ s.

Fig. 4. QA metrics of POPE at 0.3 mm.

Panels A-D depict the acquisition approach. With participant-specific auto-align, 3rd order shim artifact mitigation, and custom built 64ch MGH coil.

Panels E-H depict the relatively high fMRI quality metrics 0.3mm iso.

Panels I-J depict how POPE is pushing the gradient hardware to its limits. Short-term trajectory imperfections are mitigated by refraining from 3rd order shims that induce oscillations and by including cool-down periods between runs.

POPE's 0.30mm protocol can robustly detect fine-scale activation

Fig. 5. Activation maps of POPE at isotropic resolution of 0.30 mm.

It can be seen that POPE can robustly capture high resolution cortical brain activation. At these resolutions, functional signals can be separated from individual layer groups. Underlay EPI data show clear structural laminar features (green arrows) that can inform the interpretation of layer profiles.